

Occupant's Perception on Indoor Performance of Historical Museum: A Case Study of National Museum and Perak Museum, Malaysia

Goh Wen Shuang, Syahrul Nizam Kamaruzzaman, and Nursyahida Zulkifli

Abstract—The most crucial factors of the indoor environment performances in the museum are the staffs and visitors perception towards sick building syndrome and indoor environment quality. Besides, one of the methods used to investigate the satisfaction level on the indoor environmental performance is Post Occupancy Evaluation. The respondents are the visitors and staffs of the National Museum and Perak Museum and these museums are selected as the case study in this study. The degree of noticeable on the sick building syndrome symptom such as nose, eye, pain and aches, throat, skin and breath while the degree of likeliness on the indoor environmental performance (thermal, lighting, and air quality) in order to evaluate the level of the sick building syndrome and indoor environmental quality in the museum. This study perhaps can add to the breadth of knowledge of indoor performance in the historical building from the perspective of energy efficiency.

Keywords—Indoor environment performance, Historical museum, Malaysia, Occupants perception, Sick building syndrome.

I. INTRODUCTION

INDOOR environment quality is the character of the air and environment that contribute to the health and comfort of the occupant insides buildings. Indoor environment quality is relatively new that includes the indoor air quality, building-related illness and “sick building syndrome”. To date, the indoor environment quality expands and includes ergonomic issues such as lighting, noise, furniture, and psychological issues such as decision latitude, stressful working condition and job satisfactions [1]. Samet, Spengler and Mitchel [2] stated that the indoor environment quality also affected by indoor air constituents (primary particles, bio-aerosols and chemical); and comfort factors (temperature, air flow and humidity).

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Besides, the air and environment can be affected by chemical, biological, and physical agents from the occupant activities, building materials or ambient environment. On the other hand, there are various factors may affect the indoor environment quality consisting lighting, natural ventilation, thermal quality, indoor air quality (IAQ) and the presence volatile organic compounds (VOCs) or other contaminants and pollutants released by certain building materials.

Museum is one of the niche products of Malaysia cultural heritage tourism attraction that could affect the growth of the tourism industry in this country [3]. The indoor environmental performance or quality has recently been associated with the services for the museum management, whereby indoor environment performance required process of implementation [4]. The museums need to focus on visitor satisfaction so that able to create returning visitors in order to compete in highly competitive world of leisure and tourist attraction. Rowley [5] mentioned that the visitors satisfaction depend on the total experience of the visitors during their first visit in the museums. Even though the study on the measurement of indoor environment performance in service industries began as early as 1980s, there has not been any systematic study of how to measure the indoor environmental performance of the museums [6].

The most important thing, understands how the environment affects the visitors, publics, and workers [7]. Basically, there are several issues that affected by the poor indoor environment quality such as health problem, country reputation, and efficiency and productivity of workers in the heritage museums. Museum is one of the popular destinations among the tourists in Malaysia. The national museum is one of the popular tourist destinations in Malaysia with an average of over two million visitors per year. Previous studies have been criticized for lacking attempt to integrate the occupant perception, perhaps the visitor is the main source of measurement of indoor environmental performance. Therefore, this paper attempts to investigate the occupants' satisfaction on indoor environment performance towards two selected historical museums in Malaysia namely, Perak Museum and National Museum.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Factors and Issues of Indoor Environment Quality and Performance

The indoor environment quality is important, in fact, the inside air can be more polluted than the outside air because people spend almost 90% of time inside the building. The indoor environment quality can affect the health problems like asthma, other respiratory diseases, eyes and nose irritation. Berardil, Leoni, Marchesini, Cascella and Raffil [8] mentioned that the sick building syndromes (SBS) has become common issues in Malaysia because of the construction building design to be energy efficiency with air conditioning system but poor maintenance and services of Heating, Ventilation and Air-Conditioning (HVAC) system and resulting increasing of indoor pollutants levels.

Brudge, Hedge, Wilson, Bass and Robertson [9] stated that the SBS are influenced by the type of ventilation system with prevalence of SBS being higher in building with mechanism ventilation system compared to normal ventilation system. The SBS is related to health problems which are divided into mucous membrane system (related to eye, nose, throat, and dry skin) and general symptoms of headache and lethargy [10]. Few studies focus on the building age and indoor air pollutants characteristics with the prevalence of SBS and other health problems. It is reported that the new building is having high concentration of the total volatile organic compound (TVOC) while old buildings have poor ventilation rate with the higher carbon dioxide (CO₂) level. Therefore, this study focuses on the historical museums which are considered as old buildings.

The indoor air quality in any buildings can be compromised by microbial contaminants (e.g. Mold bacteria), chemical (carbon monoxide, formaldehyde), allergen or any mass or energy stressor that can affect the health status. The health problems usually associated with building related diseases and SBS. The building related disease include infectious diseases spread from the building services such as Legionnaires' disease and diseases spread from worker to worker within a building known as virus infection. It also includes any toxic reactions to chemicals used within the building or derived from fungus growing within the building.

The other issues of indoor environment quality (IEQ) and performance of historical museum is deterioration. The deterioration is defined as any physical or chemical change in the condition of the object and is a natural process by which an object reaches a state of physical and chemical equilibrium and with its immediate environment. The environmental agents of deterioration including chemical and physical deterioration such as temperature, humidity, light and pollution [11].

B. Reception and Perception

Human receptions are essentially the instruments that indicate whether we feel healthy or comfortable and consciously and unconsciously. These senses provide information to the brain which processed and used to send

messages with prescribed actions to the relevant parts of human body. The most obvious human senses are the sense of sight by nose, eye, skin and breathing. Table I illustrates the further explanation about the human reception

TABLE I
HUMAN RECEPTION

Reception	Description
Nose	Indoor air pollutants that can reach and activate the olfactory epithelium (in nose) are perceived as odorous. Indoor air pollutants activate the trigeminal nerve (in mucous membranes of the nasal and mouth cavities, over entire facial and forehead skin) are called irritants. The latter can cause irritation of mucosal membranes in the eye, nose or throat, dryness of eye, facial skin irritation and dryness of the skin. The possible diseases and disorder of nose are olfaction (sense of smell out of order), and nasal congestion (blockage of nasal passages due to the membranes lining the nose becoming swollen from inflamed blood vessels).
Eye	Dry eye syndrome is an eye disease that caused by decreased tear production or increased tear film evaporation causing unstable tear film. Typical symptoms are pain, redness, a pulling sensation and pressure behind the eye causing increased discomfort and sensitivity to bright light. Both eyes are usually affected and there may also be a stringy uncomfortable discharge from the eyes due to the irritation.
Skin	Infection (bacterial, viral or fungal) and inflammation (allergic reaction) can cause the skin diseases and disorder. The symptoms are itching, rashes, hives, blisters or redness. Dermatitis, which means inflammation of the skin, refer to eczema which is persistent skin conditions. These include dryness and recurring skin rashes, skin oedema, itching and dryness with possible crusting, flaking, blistering, and cracking, oozing or bleeding.
Respiratory Tract	The infection from the bacterial, viral or fungal; inflammation and damage can affect the respiratory tract. It usually caused by an external pollutant that is breathed into the lungs that cause immediate or long-term effect. The symptoms are cough, shortness of breath and asthma.

C. Perception and Satisfaction

The occupant perception is defined as a set of complex process which can recognize, organize and make sensations that received from environmental stimuli [5]. Many visitors of museums are motivated to attain a state of having been to a museum rather than enjoying being there [12]. The quality experience provided by the museum is based on the social cultural, cognitive, psychological orientation and physical and environmental [13].

Raw, Roys, and Leaman [14] suggested that the perception increases as the number of the symptoms increases with the average of 3% loss with three symptoms; and 8% loss with five symptoms. It means that when a large numbers of workers experience sign of discomfort related to the air inside their workstations, their productivity will diminish over time. The productivity is expected to suffer if the conditions are serious enough for workers to explain. The studies show that the control of environment parameters in indoor environment strongly affected the productivity of staffs of historical museums [14]. Raw et al. [14] found that the sick building syndrome and self-estimated productivity can reduce the performance ratings.

Jeong and Lee [15] concluded that the exhibition environment is the most influential factor that effect the visitor's satisfaction that includes the "method of exhibition",

“visual and locomotors accessibility”, content of exhibitions” “illumination” and “rest area”. Besides, the ambient environment consists of “density of visitors”, “noise” and “thermal comfort” have indirect effect on visitor’s satisfaction. It is proposed to properly arrange and design rest areas so that the visitors can see natural outdoor environment because some visitors may terminate their museum tour in the middle of viewing was fatigue.

D. Elements of Indoor Environment

The concepts of “indoor environment” include all aspects of the relationship between the occupants and contents of a building and their surrounding; it can be considered in terms of climatic and non climatic aspects [16]. The principal parameters aspects include thermal quality; lighting quality; air quality and aesthetic environment.

1. Thermal quality

The concepts of “indoor environment” include all aspects of the relationship between the occupants and contents of a building and their surrounding; it can be considered in terms of climatic and non climatic aspects [16]. The principal parameters aspects include thermal quality; lighting quality; air quality and aesthetic environment.

a. Temperature

The temperature determines human comfort due to the impact they several of the body’s heat transfer mechanism. An increase in temperature will cause an increase in chemical reaction rate of the deterioration of materials. The acceleration of natural processes such as the movement of water and air though stable particulates [17]. Besides, differ in temperature can cause a variety of reaction including the expansion of exhibit material and the partial dyeing up exhibits (made of wood, paper leather) can increase the fragility level of these object.

b. Humidity

Relative humidity is defined as a relationship between volume of air and the amount of water vapor at given temperature. The humidity is inversely related to the temperature [18]. For instance, in a closed system, when the temperature increases, the relative humidity decreases. While no specific standards are prescribed by law, the ideal relative humidity (RH) of air for comfort is in the range of 55-65 percent, though the range of 40-70 percent is considered acceptable. The exceed limits would be increased the tendency to ill-effects.

c. Mean Radiant Temperature

The extent of radiant heat transfer between the body and environment mainly dependent on geometric agreement of the radiating surfaces including opaque surfaces (temperature and emissivity of colour and texture), translucent surface (transmissivity, temperature and surface characteristic) and human body (surface area exposed and colour of texture of clothing [19]. The building with heavyweight ceilings and floors tend to have a lower mean radiant temperature than

those with lightweight partitioning elements due to the thermal capacity of these elements. Therefore, the building has low operative temperature in a hot weather but more comfortable in indoor environment.

d. Lighting Levels and Day Lighting

“Proper lighting can enhance task performance, while there can be energy wastage and adverse health effect of poorly designed lighting” [7].

Light is a form of energy that stimulates our sense of vision. This energy has both electrical and magnetic properties, it is known as electromagnetic radiation. Lighting includes use of both artificial light sources such as lamps and natural illumination of interior from daylight. Many studies have been conducted on the impact of lighting levels on behaviors including productivity and absenteeism of staff. The lighting level can decrease the productivity while increase the absenteeism of the staffs due to the illness occurs in workplace. In terms of deterioration, the different materials have different limit visible light level. Natural daylight consists of visible light over the frequency range of 360-760 nm, plus ultraviolet (UV) radiation at shorter wavelengths and infrared (IR) radiation at longer wavelengths. The most damaging part of the spectrum is UV radiation and causes the deterioration of the exhibits of the museum.

e. Air Quality

The air pollutant comes from contaminants produced outside and inside museums. There are two types of air pollutants; 1) particular pollutants such as dirt, dust, soot, ash, moulds and fiber; 2) gaseous pollutant such as sulphur dioxide, hydrogen sulphide, nitrogen dioxide, formaldehyde, ozone, formic and acetic acids. There are several factors that affect the indoor air quality, such as equipment and appliances used in the museum, occupant activity, building materials and outdoor air quality [20].

The air pollutants exposures are hazardous to human health and the environment. For example, 1) radon occurs naturally in parts of Europe. It can get inside buildings and may lead to the lung cancer; 2) suspended particles can cause harmful effects on health, respiratory system; 3) microbes (moulds and viruses) can contribute to the development of asthma and allergies; 4) pets and pests (dust mites, cockroaches and mice) are important indoor sources of allergens; and insufficient ventilation [20]. In general, the poor indoor air quality may affect health and work performance.

f. Aesthetic Environment

Colour is an important aspect of indoor environment. Most of the people respond to colours with their emotions and feelings and colour can be used to change the perception of the space. The colours can impact on illumination contrasts which if too high may cause discomfort. Therefore, the colour can affect the aesthetic environment of indoor comfort [16].

III. METHOD

This study was designed with the quantitative technique. The questionnaire surveys have been used have been used for the data collection method. The questionnaires were short and simple and did not take much time for the respondents to answer in order to get a high-response rate [21]. The multiple-choice questions are selected in order to obtain a short and precise question for the occupants of the historical museums. The multiple-choice questions are simple, versatile and mutually exclusive [22]. Besides, the Likert-scale is easy to use, easy to code and useful in statistical analyses. This section requires the respondents to rate on their perception on the indoor performance quality of historical museums based on their experience with 5 point Likert scale which is very dissatisfied to very satisfy. The questionnaire is divided into 5 sections which are socio-demographic information; perception on gallery area; perception on indoor environment quality, perception on "sick building syndrome" symptoms; health status; and job information.

The questionnaires designed for both museum staffs and visitors (occupants) are same for the first five sections, whereas section 6 is only included in the survey forms distributed to the museum staffs. A total of 450 questionnaires were distributed to occupants (staffs and visitors) of the historical museums which are National Museum, Kuala Lumpur and Perak Museum, Perak. Out of 450 questionnaires, 270 set of questionnaires were distributed to the visitors of National Museum, while 180 set of questionnaires were distributed to the Perak Museum. However, only 404 questionnaires were returned and valid for further analyses. The responds consist of 255 questionnaires are from National Museum, Kuala Lumpur and 149 questionnaires are from Perak Museum. The respondents should be above 18 years old as they are more understand the requirements of the questions and they rate their perception based on their experience during the visit to the museums. The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents during the weekends and public holidays within time frame of one month because there will be large number of visitors during weekend compared to weekdays.

IV. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

A. Perception and Gallery Area

Through the literature, the authors had identified 12 aspects that determine the perception on gallery area which are content of exhibition, methods of exhibition, quality of exhibition, explanation of exhibition, locomotors accessibility, circulation, rest area, density of exhibits, density of visitors, perceived learning, perceived enjoyment and total staying time in the gallery. The mean values were computed in order to rank visitor's perception on the gallery area. To rank some of the variables, the calculation of central tendency using mean was carried out. Seven-point scales used in the questionnaires were transformed to mean reading in order to determine the ranks of the variable [21]. Table 2 presents the mean values of the visitors' perception on gallery area.

TABLE II
RANKING OF VISITOR'S PERCEPTION ON GALLERY AREA

Rank	Perception on gallery	Mean value
1	Content of exhibition	6.09
2	Quality of exhibition	6.03
3	Methods of exhibition	5.96
4	Perceived enjoyment	5.96
5	Explanation of exhibition	5.93
6	Perceived learning	5.92
7	Circulation	5.91
8	Total staying time	5.84
9	Locomotors accessibility	5.79
10	Density of exhibits	5.69
11	Density of visitors	5.63
12	Rest area	5.45

Table II shows the mean value and ranking of the perception on gallery area among the visitors. Majority of the visitors are agreed that content of the exhibition has the highest mean value indicated 6.09 while the lowest degree of likeliness among 12 aspects of perception on gallery area is rest area with the mean value is 5.45. The perception on the gallery area can be determined the need and demand of the building users. The perception on the gallery area are at the satisfy level as the mean values for all the aspects of perception on the gallery area are above 5.00.

B. Perception on Indoor Environment Quality (IEQ)

The indoor environment quality can be determined by the thermal quality, lighting quality and air quality. The mean value is computed to determine the perception on the indoor environment quality of museum. All the perception of visitors is more than 5 and approach to 6, it means that the visitors are agreed with the indoor environment performance of museum. Table III illustrates the mean values of the visitors' perception on indoor environment quality.

TABLE III
RANKING OF VISITOR'S PERCEPTION ON IEQ

Rank	Indoor Environment Quality (IEQ)	Mean value
1	Air movement	5.89
2	Indoor temperature	5.85
3	Cleanliness	5.84
4	Relative humidity	5.82
5	Clarity	5.77
6	Freshness	5.71
7	Brightness	5.68
8	Naturalness appearance of exhibits	5.65
9	Odour	5.65
10	Uniformity of lighting distribution	5.62
11	Indoor temperature	5.59
12	Lighting	5.57

Table III shows that the relative air movement has the highest degree of likeliness with the mean value of 5.89 (like slightly to like moderate) whereas the lighting has the lowest degree of likeliness among 12 items of perception on indoor environment quality with the mean value of 5.57 (like slightly to like moderate). The perception of the visitors on the indoor environment quality (IEQ) can be determined the need and

demand of the building users. The perception on the indoor environment quality in the historical museums are at the satisfy level as the mean values for all the aspects of perception on the indoor environment quality are above 5.00.

C. Sick Building Syndrome

The sick building syndrome consists of six main senses which are sinus and nose; eyes; pain and aches; throat; skin; and breathe. The 5 point scales were used to determine the sick building syndrome from indoor museum environment where 1 is unnoticeable and 5 is very noticeable. Table IV illustrates the information on sick building syndrome (SBS) from indoor museum environment. The mean values show that the perception on these senses mostly are between 1 and 2 indicated that the sensibility of symptoms is from unnoticeable approach rarely noticeable on SBS of indoor museum environment.

TABLE IV
RANKING OF SICK BUILDING SYNDROME ON VISITORS' PERCEPTION

Rank	Sick Building Syndrome (SBS)	Mean value
1	Tired eyes	1.25
2	Tiredness	1.20
	Dry skin	1.17
3	Sneezing	1.17
	Dry eye	1.17
	Runny nose	1.17
7	Dizzy	1.16
8	Headache	1.14
9	Blurred vision	1.13
	Sore throat	1.13
11	Cough	1.12
	Glare	1.12
	Itchy nose	1.12
14	Itchy skin	1.09
	Wheezing	1.09
	Breathing difficulty	1.09
17	Itchy eye	1.08
18	Rash	1.07
19	Stress	1.05
	Anxiety	1.05
21	Chest tightness	1.04
22	Tension/ nervousness	1.03

Table IV illustrates the ranking of sick building syndrome on visitors' perception. It shows that the tired eyes have the highest mean value of 1.25 whereas tension or nervousness shows the lowest scale among 22 symptoms with a mean value of 1.03. It can be concluded that the most of the symptoms of sick building syndrome were unnoticeable or rarely noticeable and the different in means values of each symptoms are relatively small.

D. MANOVA Test

The multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) is used in analyzing the data in this study. The MANOVA is a type of multivariate analysis that involves more than one dependent variable at a time. In this case, MANOVA test was carried out to compare the effect of the thermal quality, lighting quality, air quality, indoor environment quality and sick building syndrome towards the occupants (staffs and visitors).

TABLE V
MULTIVARIATE TEST OF OCCUPANTS

Effect	Dependent variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Occupant	Thermal Quality	0.01	1	0.01		.95
	Lighting Quality	0.06	1	0.06		.83
	Air Quality	6.96	1	6.96		.02
	Indoor Environment Quality	0.60	1	0.60		.42
	Sick Building Syndrome	0.62	1	0.62		.01

Table V shows the analysis test of between-subject effect if the occupants. The results show that there is a significant difference between occupants (staffs and visitors) on air quality [$F(1,437) = 5.28, p = .02 (p < .05)$] and sick building syndrome [$F(1,437) = 6.79, p = .01 (p < .05)$]. As conclusion, the types of occupants affect the perception on air quality and sick building syndrome.

TABLE VI
MEANS OF OCCUPANTS

Dependent Variable	Occupant	Mean	Std. Error
Thermal Quality	Visitor	5.84	.06
	Staff	5.85	.19
Lighting Quality	Visitor	5.66	.06
	Staff	5.70	.20
Air Quality	Visitor	5.70	.06
	Staff	5.22	.20
Indoor Environment Quality	Visitor	5.72	.05
	Staff	5.58	.17
Sick Building Syndrome	Visitor	1.12	.02
	Staff	1.26	.05

Table VI illustrated the estimated marginal means of visitor and staff respectively. The staffs' estimated marginal mean of sick building syndrome is higher than the visitors, indicated that the staffs are more aware to sick building syndrome than the visitors. Definitely, the staying time of the staffs in the historical museum is longer than the visitors. Normally, a visitor only spent less than 2 hours to visit the museum whereas the staffs need to stay at least seven hours per day in their working environment. Thus, they are more contactable with the indoor museum environment and the staffs supposedly should more aware and noticeable toward the sick building syndrome.

However, the visitors have higher degree of likeliness to the perception on air quality inside the museum compare to the staffs. This could be happened as the museum is permanent working environment for the staffs. Therefore, they have higher requirement or standards towards the indoor museum air quality. Moreover, the visitors are fewer requests to the ideal air quality of museums. They might only ask for an indoor museum environment which free from dust and not smelly, perhaps runny nose sneezing not happened during the visit.

V. CONCLUSION

Post occupancy evaluation is one of the best ways to define the user's need and demand on indoor environment quality of historical museums. There is a high response rate was obtained from the National Museum, Kuala Lumpur and Perak Museum. The occupants do experience certain symptoms of sick building syndrome during their visit in the museum. Most of the staffs felt that the symptoms on sinus and nose while the visitors had tired eye and fatigue after the visit. Besides, the staffs and visitors have distinctive time contact with the indoor museum environment. It is due to the visitors only spent less than 2 hours inside the museums, so the staffs experience the sick building syndrome is higher than the visitors. Future researchers on the interest of the post occupancy evaluation on indoor museum environment should include the measurement and analytical study to correlate and identify the occupants' satisfaction level with the actual level of indoor museum environment served.

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